

The Structure and Stereochemistry of Lantanilic Acid. A New Triterpene Isolated from *Lantana camara*

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The structure of lantanilic acid, a new triterpene isolated from the leaves of *Lantana camara*, has been finally established as 22 β - β , β -dimethylacryloyloxy-3,25-epoxy-3 α -hydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (1a).

THE plant *Lantana camara* belonging to the family Verbenaceae is a native of tropical America, now naturalised in India. It grows wild in many parts of India. It is known to cause severe photosensitivity and icterus¹ in sheep. Chemical investigations by Louw² and Barton *et al.*³ led to the isolation of lantadene A (rehmanic acid), one of the causative factors, and also another triterpene lantadene B. Re-examination of the plant *Lantana camara* collected from suburbs of Calcutta by Barua *et al.* led to the isolation of two novel triterpene acids called lantic acid^{4,5}, and lantanolic acid^{6,7}, besides 3-keto-ursolic acid. The isolation and structure of another new triterpene called lantanilic acid was also reported by the same authors in a preliminary communication^{8,9}.

Further studies on the structure of the compound has now been carried out and the present paper details all the experiments leading to the final structure and stereochemistry of lantanilic acid.

Several new triterpenes from *L. camara* have been reported by John *et al.*¹⁰ and Noel *et al.*¹¹.

Lantanilic acid (1a), was isolated from the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of *L. camara* by repeated column chromatography over silica gel. On treatment with ethereal diazomethane, it formed a methyl ester (1b). The uv spectrum of both 1a and 1b showed absorption maxima at 218 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.24) which indicated the presence of β , β -dimethylacryloyl moiety (*cf.* lantadene B³) in lantanilic acid. This was further confirmed by the mass spectrum of methyl lantanilate which did not show the molecular ion peak at m/z 582 but showed a peak at m/z 482 for the (M-100)⁺ ion arising by the loss of a molecule of β , β -dimethylacrylic acid. The mass spectrum also showed a peak at m/z 83 for the ion $\text{Me}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{C}\equiv\text{O}^+$ and a peak at m/z 260 for the ion species *a* formed by retro Diels-Alder fragmentation of the molecule. Lantanilic acid (1a) on saponification with 5% ethanolic caustic potash furnished β , β -dimethylacrylic acid and a new triterpene acid called lantaninilic acid (1c). With ethereal diazomethane, it formed the methyl ester

(1d). Uv spectrum of methyl lantanilate (1d) showed absorption maxima at 206 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.8) indicating the presence of a trisubstituted double bond. Its ir spectrum showed bands at 3450, 3250 (OH), 1727 cm^{-1} (COOMe). The mass spectrum of methyl lantanilate (1d) did not show the molecular ion peak at m/z 500 but showed peak at m/z 482 for the ion species (M-18)⁺ arising by the loss of a molecule of water. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of methyl lantanilate [peak at m/z 260(*a*), 201, 482, 299(*b*) and 239(*c*)] showed a close similarity with methyl lantanolate^{6,7} (m/z 262, 203, 484, 301 and 241), the differences of 2 mass units being due to the loss of water from ring E of 1d. It should be pointed out here that the mass spectra of methyl lantate, methyl lantanolate and methyl lantanilate, each containing a hemiketal system in ring A, showed peaks at m/z 241 (in case of methyl lantate and methyl lantanolate) and m/z 239 (in case of methyl lantanilate, ion species *c*) formed by unusual cleavage through ring B. The peaks at m/z 241 or 239 is far more intense than the peaks at m/z 262 or 260(*a*) formed by the usual r.D.A. fragmentation involving the 12:13 double bond. For methyl lantanilate, the r.D.A. fragment ion *a* (m/z 260) was about 34% of the peak at m/z 299 (*b*) and 239 (*c*), respectively formed by the cleavage through ring B. This type of cleavage through ring B leading to the formation of ion species *b* and *c* has been observed in the other derivatives of methyl lantanilate having a hydroxymethylene or an aldehyde group at C-10 and the same pattern has been observed in case of methyl lantate and methyl lantanolate. This interesting and characteristic fragmentation pattern may be of diagnostic value in locating an oxygen function at C-10 in triterpenes of Δ^{12} -oleanane series.

Methyl lantanilate on refluxing with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine yielded a mono-oxime. As the nmr spectrum of methyl lantanilate did not show any signal for an aldehydic proton the carbonyl function should be a keto group.

- 1a $R_1 = R_2 = H$
 $R_3 = OCCH=C(Me)_2$
 1b $R_1 = H, R_2 = Me$
 $R_3 = OCCH=C(Me)_2$
 1c $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 1d $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = Me$
 1e $R_1 = R_2 = Me, R_3 = H$
 1f $R_1 = H, R_2 = Me,$
 $R_3 = OCOC(=O)H$

(d) m/z 315

Lantaninic acid on treatment with bromine in acetic acid at room temperature yielded a monobromo- γ -lactone (2), like oleanolic acid¹³. Its ir spectrum (nujol) showed only a single band at 1755 cm^{-1} for a γ -lactone ring and there was no other band in the carbonyl region for the keto group and this clearly showed that the carbonyl group in lantaninic acid is not free but forms part of a hemiketal system. The formation of the monobromo- γ -lactone like oleanolic acid clearly showed that the carboxyl group in lantaninic acid is located at C-17 and the double bond at 12 : 13-position.

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Methyl lantaninate on refluxing with methanolic sulphuric acid furnished a ketal (1e), indicating the presence of hemiketal system in lantaninic acid (cf. methyl lantanolate⁷ and methyl lantate⁴). The ketal (1e) on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid in tetrahydrofuran gave back methyl lantaninate. The experiments so far described leave no doubt that the keto group in lantaninic acid does not

exist in the free state but forms part of a hemiketal system.

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Methyl lantaninate (1d) on KBH_4 reduction yielded two epimeric products. The major constituent called triol-A, (4a), was obtained in a pure state. Its mass spectrum showed a weak molecular ion peak at m/z 502 and two prominent peaks at m/z 484 ($\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$)⁺ and 466 ($\text{M}-2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)⁺. There were also peaks at m/z 453 and 435 due to the ions ($\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$)⁺ and ($\text{M}-2\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$)⁺, such peaks arising out of loss of 31 mass unit (CH_2OH), are usually observed in the mass spectra of triterpenes having hydroxymethylene group¹⁵. The minor product triol-B (4b), which was not isolated in pure state, is presumed to be the 3 α -axial isomer as it moved faster than triol-A in tlc¹⁴. The nmr spectrum of triol-A in CDCl_3 showed a singlet at δ 4.01 for the two protons of hydroxy methylene group at C-10 and a triplet at δ 3.86 (1H, J 3 Hz) for 22 α -H and a multiplet (1H) at δ 3.2 for 3 α -H, the low coupling constant (J 3 Hz) of the signal at δ 3.86 clearly indicated that the secondary hydroxyl group at C-22 must be β . The triol-A on heating with acetic anhydride in pyridine on steam bath yielded a triacetate (4c). Its mass spectrum did not show the molecular ion peak at m/z 628 but showed a strong peak at m/z 568 for the ion ($\text{M}-\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$)⁺. There were also peaks at m/z 508 ($\text{M}-2\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$)⁺ and 448 ($\text{M}-3\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$)⁺, and at m/z 435 for the ion ($\text{M}-2\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{COCH}_3$). Its nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 showed singlet at δ 4.46 for the two protons α - to the primary acetoxy group ($\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), a triplet at δ 4.99 (1H, J 3 Hz) for the 22 α -H and a multiplet at δ 4.54 for the 3 α -H. There were sharp singlets at δ 2.04 (6H) and 1.93 (3H) for the three acetoxy methyl groups ($\text{O}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$).

On refluxing with selenium dioxide in glacial acetic acid, triol-A triacetate furnished a product which could not be isolated in a pure state. However, it showed a triple absorption maxima at 248, 252 and 260 nm, characteristic of an heteroannular transoid diene system. Mild saponification of the above product with ethanolic caustic potash (3%) at room temperature yielded a compound, $C_{31}H_{48}O_5$ (M^+ 500). It also showed triple absorption maxima at 243, 252, 260 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.37, 4.41 and 4.42, respectively) characteristic of $\Delta^{11:12}$, 13:18-diene of the oleanene series¹⁵ which are known to show absorption maxima in the region 240, 250 and 260 nm. This experiment leads to the conclusion that lantaninic acid and hence lantanilic acid is a triterpene of the Δ^{12} -oleanane series for members of the corresponding ursane series¹⁶ are not susceptible to selenium dioxide oxidation under the above condition.

The ketal (1e) on oxidation with CrO_3 -pyridine complex yielded a keto compound (5), which, as expected, did not respond to Zimmermann's colour test¹⁷ for a 3-keto group. Saponification of 5 with ethanolic caustic potash (10%) gave the nor-compound (6). The formation of the nor-compound requires the presence of a keto group at β -position with respect to the carbomethoxyl group in compound 5 and hence a hydroxyl group at the β -position with respect to caboxyl group in lantanilic acid. On the basis of the data so far discussed, the secondary hydroxyl group in lantanilic acid could be located either at C-22 or C-16 for the carboxyl group was earlier located at C-17.

Oxidation of a mixture of triol-A and triol-B with CrO_3 -pyridine complex gave a product 7. Its mass spectrum showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 496. There were also peaks at m/z 478 and 437 corresponding to the ion $(M-H_2O)^+$ and $(M-COOCH_3)^+$, respectively. There was also peak at m/z 276 for the ion species arising out of normal r.D.A. fragmentation involving the 12:13 double bond which by loss of 59 mass unit ($COOCH_3$)

yielded the ion at m/z 217. The unusual type of fragmentation through ring B gave rise to ion species (d), which gave rise to the peak at m/z 255 by loss of 60 mass units ($COOCH_3 + H$).

The diketoaldehyde (7) on refluxing with ethylene glycol and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in benzene furnished a product, m.p. 311-323°. Its mass spectrum, however, showed a strong peak at m/z 584 and 540 indicating the product to be a mixture of a diketal, $C_{35}H_{52}O_7$ (M^+ 584) and a monoketal, $C_{35}H_{48}O_6$ (M^+ 540).

The ketal (1e), on treatment with $POCl_3$ in pyridine yielded the dehydro product (8). This on hydrogenation gave a product, which was identified as the ketal of methyl lantanolate^{6,7}, by comparison of its and nmr spectra with an authentic sample. This on deketalisation with hydrochloric acid in tetrahydrofuran gave a product which was identified as methyl lantanolate. The conversion of methyl lantanilate to methyl lantanolate as described above proved the structure of lantanilic acid except for the position of the secondary hydroxyl group.

On heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride on steam-bath for 1 h methyl lantanilate yielded a mixture of diacetate (3) and a monoacetate (1f). The latter on further heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine for 30 h yielded the diacetate (3).

Acetylation of methyl lantanilate at 0°, however furnished a mixture of monoacetate (1f) and unreacted methyl lantanilate. The mass spectrum of the diacetate did not show the molecular ion peak at m/z 584 but there was a peak at m/z 524 for the ion species $(M-CH_3COOH)^+$, besides peaks at m/z 464 and 451 for the ions $(M-2MeCOOH)^+$ and $(M-MeCOOH-CH_2OCOMe)^+$, respectively. The loss of 73 mass unit (CH_2OCOMe) in the latter indicated the presence of a primary acetoxy group in the diacetate (cf. aescigenin pentaacetate¹⁸ and erythrodioldiacetate¹⁹). The mass spectrum of the monoacetate (1f) showed a weak molecular ion peak at

m/z 542. The nmr spectrum (CDCl_3 , 60 MHz) of the monoacetate was in conformity with the structure 1f. There were two pairs of doublets centred at δ 4.26 (J 9 Hz) and 3.9 (J 9 Hz) for the two non-equivalent methylene protons ($\text{CH}_2\text{-O-C-O}$) of the hemiketal system. The signals at δ 4.26 and 3.9 were both split further (J 2.5 Hz and J 1 Hz, respectively) due to long range coupling with one of the C-1 protons (*cf.* nmr spectrum of methyl lantanolate⁷). The triplet centred at δ 4.95 (1H, J 3.5 Hz) was assigned to 22 α -H. The low coupling constant (3.5 Hz) indicated β -orientation of the secondary hydroxyl group at C-22. The C-12 vinyl proton signal appeared at δ 5.41 (1 H, t).

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The nmr spectrum of methyl lantanilate closely resembles that of methyl lantanolate, excepting a triplet at δ 3.91, which is attributed to C-22 α -carbinyl proton which is absent in methyl lantanolate. It has been reported earlier by Barua *et al.*¹⁰ that the 16- β -H (CH-O-CO-Me) of diacetyl methyl echinocystate gave rise to a signal at δ 5.69 which is much further down-field than the signal observed at δ 4.95 due to proton attached to the carbon bearing the secondary acetoxy group (CHOCOME) in the monoacetate (1f). On the basis of the above observations it was concluded that the secondary hydroxyl group in lantanilic acid is located not at C-16 but at C-22 and hence the structure of lantanilic acid should be 1c.

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In order to obtain further evidences to finally locate the secondary hydroxyl group at C-22 the following experiments were carried out. It has been mentioned earlier that the ketal of methyl lantanilate (1e) on dehydration with POCl_3 in pyridine furnished a dehydroproduct (8) which on hydrogenation gave the ketal of methyl lantanolate. This conversion clearly showed that during dehydrogenation no rearrangement took place. As there were two possible locations for the secondary hydroxyl groups at C-22 or C-16, the dehydro compound (8)

should therefore contain either a 21 : 22- or a 15 : 16-double bond. Now, the 21 : 22-double bond in Δ^{15} -oleanane skeleton undergo *cis*-glycolation with osmium tetroxide. Both Meyer *et al.*²⁰ and Smith *et al.*²¹ carried out partial synthesis of soyasapogenol-A-diacetate (10) from soyasapogenol-C-diacetate (9). Both the groups of workers got the β -isomer as the major product and the α -isomer was obtained in very poor yield as its formation requires the attack by the reagent from the more hindered α -face of the ring E. We have prepared methyl 3-acetyl-15 : 16-dehydroechinocystate (11) by treatment of methyl-3-acetylechincocystate (methyl 3-acetyl-16 α -hydroxyolean-12-ene-28-oate) with POCl_3 in pyridine and we made several attempts for glycolation of the 15 : 16-double bond with OsO_4 but only recovered the unreacted material and the results clearly showed the non-susceptibility of the 15 : 16-double bond to OsO_4 treatment, but the dehydro compound (8) yielded a mixture of glycols (12a and 12b) on treatment with OsO_4 of which the former was the major product and could be obtained in a pure crystalline state.

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The nmr spectrum (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) of the glycolated product (12a) showed two carbinyl proton signals at δ 3.40 (d, J 4.0 Hz) and 3.8 (d, J 4.0 Hz) which was partly overlapped by one of the signals of the non-equivalent protons of the methylene group of the ketal system. The above two signals were assigned to 21 α -H (δ 3.40) and 22 α -H (δ 3.8), respectively for reasons stated below.

Djerassi *et al.*²² have shown that 21-hydroxyl group whether α - or β - (*cf.* methyl machaerinate²²) could be acetylated easily in the cold with acetic anhydride and pyridine but 22- β -hydroxyl group could not be acetylated under such a condition (*cf.* rhenanic acid⁹). On acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath, 12a furnished the diacetate (12c). Its nmr spectrum (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) showed signals at δ 5.3 (d, J 4 Hz) and 4.8 (d, J 4 Hz) which were attributed to the 22- α H and 21- β H, respectively. The two acetoxy methyl signals appeared as a singlet at δ 2.10 (6H). It may be mentioned here that the signal for 22- α H of methyl lantanilate appeared at δ 3.91 which shifted to δ 4.95 on acetylation (*cf.* nmr spectrum of monoacetyl methyl lantanilate, 1f). In case of the diacetate (12c) the 22 α -H proton appears at δ 5.3 (d, J 4 Hz) which is slightly more down-field than 22 α -H signal observed at δ 4.95 in case of monoacetylmethyl lantanilate (1f). We have observed

that the 21α -H signal in the nmr spectrum of methyl $3\beta,21\beta$ -diacetylolean-12-ene-28-oate (3, 21-diacetyl methyl machaerinate) appears as a pair of doublet centred at δ 4.79 and this would support the assignment of the signal at δ 4.8 in the nmr spectra of the diacetate (12c) to the 21α -H and hence the signal at δ 5.3 to the 22α -H. Treatment of 12a with acetic anhydride and pyridine at 0° furnished a product (12d). Its nmr spectrum (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) showed signals at δ 4.8 (d, J 4 Hz) which is attributed to 21α -H and the acetoxymethyl signal appeared as a singlet at δ 2.19 (3H). The 22α -H proton signal was overlapped with that of one of the methylene protons of ketal system. The formation of the monoacetate (12d) indicate that one of the two OH groups is more hindered than the other. It was mentioned earlier that 21 -OH whether α - or β - can be easily acetylated, whereas 22β -OH is comparatively more hindered and cannot be acetylated under mild condition. If the vicinal glycol system in compound 12a is β -, then acetylation under mild condition is expected to give the 21 -acetate (12d) as was found actually to be the case, whereas in case of glycol system as in compound 12b both the 21α -OH and the 22α -OH should undergo acetylation under mild condition. Based on these arguments, we propose the structure of 12a for the major product of osmylation of the corresponding dehydro compound (8). This means that the $21 : 22$ -double bond on osmylation gives mainly β -*cis* glycol as observed by Meyer *et al.*²⁰ and Smith *et al.*²¹. The formation of above product is only possible if one of the double bonds in 8 is susceptible to the attack by OsO_4 reagent and as a corollary the secondary hydroxyl group in lantanilic acid is located at C-22 and not at C-16. The above experiment clearly establish the structure of lantanilic acid as 1c.

Lantanilic acid has been shown previously to be the β, β -dimethylacryloyl derivative of lantanilic acid (1c). The nmr spectrum (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) of lantanilic acid showed two pairs of doublets

centred at δ 4.22 (1H, J 9 Hz) and 3.89 (1H, J 9 Hz) for the two non-equivalent methylene protons ($\text{CH}_2\text{-O-C-O}$) of the hemiketal system. The signals at δ 4.22 were further split (J 2.5 Hz) and the others at δ 3.89 were also split (J 1 Hz) due to long range coupling with one of the C-1 protons. In this region there was a very close similarity in the nmr spectrum of lantanilic acid with that of methyl lantanilate. The triplet centred at δ 3.91 due to the 22α -H found in nmr spectrum of methyl lantanilate was, as expected, absent in the nmr spectrum of lantanilic acid but instead was shifted to δ 5.01 (1H, t, J 3 Hz, $\text{CH-O-CO-CH}=\text{CMe}_2$) due to esterification of the C-22 β -hydroxyl group which indicated that the β, β -dimethylacryloyloxy moiety in lantanilic acid is located at C-22. In the high field region the nmr spectrum of lantanilic acid showed five sharp singlets at δ 0.77 (3H), 0.88 (3H), 0.5 (3H), 1.01 (6H) and 1.14 (3H) for six tertiary methyl groups. The vinyl proton signal of the β, β -dimethylacryloyloxy moiety ($\text{O-CO-CH}=\text{CMe}_2$) appeared at δ 5.56 (m, 1H). The signals for the two β -methyl groups ($\text{O-CO-CH}=\text{CMe}_2$) appeared, as expected^{23,24} at δ 1.83 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz) and 2.12 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz), respectively.

Thus the spectral and other data presented above clearly establish the structure and stereochemistry of lantanilic acid as 1a.

Experimental

All the melting points were recorded in a bisulphate bath and are uncorrected.

Isolation of lantanilic acid: Air-dried powdered leaves (885 g) of *Lantana camara* were exhaustively Soxhleted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) for 50 h. The residue left after removal of the solvent was taken up in ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with aqueous caustic potash solution (2%) and then with water. The alkaline extract was acidified with dilute HCl and the precipitated gummy material was taken up in ether and the ether layer was washed with water and distilled. The residue thus obtained was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. The column was eluted successively with solvents of increasing polarity. The chloroform eluate yielded a fraction which was crystallised from methanol. The above crystalline compound (lantanilic acid, 1a) was found to be homogeneous in tlc (solvent system: benzene-chloroform-methanol = 62 : 33 : 3, v/v), m.p. 277-279(d) (Found: C, 73.45; H, 9.42. $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_6$ calcd. C, 73.91; H, 9.21%; Mol. wt. 568); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 176^\circ$ (Py).

Preparation of methyl ester of lantanilic acid: methyl lantanilate (1b)

Lantanilic acid (100 mg) was dissolved in methanol (50 ml) and cooled to 0° . To it ethereal solution of diazomethane was added and left overnight. It was worked up in the usual way and the product was purified by column chromatography

over silica gel and was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture, m.p. 183-185° (Found: C, 74.28; H, 9.51; m/z 482 (M-100)⁺. C₂₈H₃₄O₈ calcd. C, 74.19; H, 9.34%; mol. wt. 582); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 173.5^\circ$ (Py).

Saponification of lantanilic acid: Lantanilic acid (500 mg) was dissolved in 5% ethanolic caustic potash solution (30 ml) and refluxed on steam bath for 1 h. Ethanol was removed on steam bath by keeping the volume constant by addition of water and then acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 5% aqueous NaHCO₃ solution and then with 5% aqueous KOH solution. The bicarbonate extract was acidified with dilute HCl and then extracted with ether. Ether layer was washed with water and distilled. The residue was distilled (b.p. 100-107° at 20 mm pressure) when a white solid material, m.p. 60-67° was obtained. It was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 70°, and identified as β,β -dimethylacrylic acid by comparison of tlc according to Barua *et al.*²⁵ and m.m.p. with an authentic sample.

The caustic potash extract was acidified with HCl and the precipitate was filtered and washed with water and crystallised from methanol (lantanilic acid, 1c), m.p. 293-296° (Found: C, 74.42; H, 9.82. C₃₀H₄₀O₈ calcd. C, 74.04; H, 9.53%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 155^\circ$ (EtOH).

The above acid was esterified with diazomethane in the usual way. The product was dissolved in chloroform and filtered through a column of silica gel and crystallised from aqueous ethanol and also from aqueous methanol (methyl lantanilate, 1d), m.p. 227-229° (Found: C, 74.71; H, 9.89; m/z 482 (M-H₂O)⁺. C₃₁H₄₂O₈ calcd. C, 74.36; H, 9.66%; mol. wt. 500); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 151.9^\circ$ (CHCl₃).

Preparation of mono-oxime of methyl lantanilate: Methyl lantanilate (200 mg) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (300 mg) were dissolved in pyridine (6 ml) and heated on steam bath for 6 h. It was then diluted with ice-water, and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol and aqueous methanol, m.p. 196-199° (Found: C, 71.24; H, 9.62; N, 2.56. C₃₁H₄₂O₈N calcd. C, 71.53; H, 9.80; N, 2.78%).

Preparation of bromo-lactone of lantanilic acid (2): To a solution of lantanilic acid (200 mg) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), a solution of sodium acetate (800 mg) was added. It was stirred while a solution of bromine in acetic acid (3%, 10 ml) was added dropwise and then was left overnight at room temperature. Excess of bromine was discharged by sodium thiosulphate solution and then the mixture was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. The residue was crystallised from methanol and then from chloroform-methanol mixture, m.p. 245-250°(d.) (Found: C, 74.89; H, 9.42. C₃₀H₄₀O₈Br calcd. C, 74.67; H, 9.79%).

Preparation of the ketal (1e): Methyl lantanilate (3 g) was dissolved in dry MeOH (100 ml) and to it conc. H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was added and refluxed for 1 h, and then cooled to room temperature and left for 2 h. The crystals thus obtained were filtered, washed with water and then with methanol. The product obtained showed two spots in tlc (solvent system, benzene : methanol=48 : 2, v/v), one of which corresponded to that of unreacted methyl lantanilate. The above material was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Benzene-chloroform (2 : 1) eluate gave a crystalline residue showing a single spot in tlc. It was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and methanol (1e), m.p. 284-287° (Found: C, 74.89; H, 9.42; M⁺ 514. C₃₃H₅₀O₈ calcd. C, 74.67; H, 9.79%; mol. wt. 514).

Further elution of the column with chloroform and methanol mixture yielded unreacted methyl lantanilate.

The above ketal (1e, 80 mg) was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran and to it was added dilute HCl (5%, 3.5 ml) and refluxed on steam bath for 5 h and then poured on to crushed ice. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous methanol, m.p. 227-229°. It was found to be identical with methyl lantanilate (1d).

KBH₄ reduction of methyl lantanilate: Methyl lantanilate (500 mg) was dissolved in methanol (25 ml). KBH₄ (500 mg) was added to the above solution and was left overnight. It was poured on to crushed ice, acidified with dilute HCl, and the precipitate was filtered and dried. Tlc showed it to contain a major compound and another compound in traces. The former could be obtained in a pure state by crystallisation. It was repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of chloroform-benzene and then from benzene, (Triol-A, 4a), m.p. 216-218° (Found: C, 74.15; H, 10.4; M⁺ 502. C₃₁H₄₀O₈ calcd. C, 74.06; H, 10.02%; mol. wt. 502).

Acetylation of triol-A: A solution of triol-A (4a, 50 mg) in pyridine (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) was heated on steam bath for 24 h. It was poured on to crushed ice, the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was dissolved in benzene and filtered through a column of silica gel, crystallised from benzene and petroleum mixture. (4c), m.p. 234-236° (Found: C, 70.31; H, 9.23; m/z 568 (M-CH₃COOH). C₃₇H₅₈O₈ calcd. C, 70.67; H, 8.98%; mol. wt. 628).

SeO₂ oxidation of triol-A-triacetate: To a solution of triol-A-triacetate (4c, 600 mg) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) freshly prepared SeO₂ (600 mg) was added and refluxed on sand bath for 5 h, filtered hot and the filtrate was diluted with water. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dissolved in benzene and adsorbed on a column of silica gel. The benzene-chloroform (3 : 1) eluate gave an amorphous material which could

not be crystallised but showed single spot in tlc (solvent system, benzene-chloroform-methanol = 45 : 4 : 1, v/v).

The above product was saponified with 3% ethanolic caustic potash at room temperature and worked up in usual way and then crystallised from aqueous methanol, m.p. 261-265°(d.) (Found : C, 74.65 ; H, 9.99. $C_{21}H_{48}O_8$ calcd. C, 74.36 ; H, 9.66%).

Oxidation of the ketal (1e) with CrO_3 -pyridine complex : The ketal (1e, 340 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (12 ml) and then treated with CrO_3 -pyridine complex (prepared by adding 100 mg CrO_3 to 15 ml pyridine) at 0° and kept at room temperature overnight. It was poured on to crushed ice, and the precipitate was filtered and washed with water. It was dissolved in chloroform and the solution was filtered through a column of silica gel and solvent was evaporated. The residue was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, (keto compound 5), m.p. 241-243° (Found : C, 74.62 ; H, 9.71. $C_{22}H_{48}O_8$ calcd. C, 74.96 ; H, 9.41%).

Saponification of the keto compound (5) : nor-compound (6) : The ketone (5, 200 mg) was refluxed with 10% ethanolic caustic potash (15 ml) for 4.5 h. It was then diluted with water, and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and then crystallised from a mixture of chloroform-methanol (6) m.p. 235-237° (Found : C, 79.21 ; H, 10.5. $C_{20}H_{44}O_8$ calcd. C, 79.44 ; H, 10.32%).

Oxidation of the mixture of triol-A and triol-B with CrO_3 -pyridine complex : diketoaldehyde (7) : A mixture of triol-A and triol-B (425 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (22 ml) and cooled to 0°. To it was added CrO_3 -pyridine complex (prepared from 500 mg CrO_3 and 25 ml pyridine) at 0°. It was stirred for 3 h and kept overnight at room temperature, then poured on crushed ice and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over a column of silica gel. C_6H_6 - $CHCl_3$ (1 : 1) eluate gave a product, which was crystallised from ethanol (95%), $C_{21}H_{44}O_8$ (diketoaldehyde, 7), m.p. 232-235° (Found : M^+ , 496. calcd. $C_{21}H_{44}O_8$: M, 496).

Treatment of diketoaldehyde (7) with ethylene glycol and p-toluenesulphonic acid : The diketoaldehyde on refluxing with ethylene glycol and p-toluenesulphonic acid in benzene on steam bath for 6 h gave a product, m.p. 311-323°. Mass spectrum showed that it was a mixture of mono- and di-ketal ; (Found : M^+ , 584 and M^+ , 540. calcd. $C_{28}H_{52}O_7$: M, 584, diketal ; for $C_{23}H_{48}O_6$: M, 540, monoketal).

Treatment of the ketal (1e) with $POCl_3$ in pyridine : dehydro compound (8) : The ketal (1e ; 1 g) was dissolved in pyridine (25 ml) and cooled to 0°. $POCl_3$ (10 ml) was added to the solution. It was then heated on steam bath for 1.5 h, cooled to room temperature and poured on to crushed

ice. The white precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) eluate gave crystalline material which was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, (8), m.p. 221-223° (Found : C, 77.11 ; H, 9.92. $C_{22}H_{48}O_4$ calcd. C, 77.38 ; H, 9.74%).

Hydrogenation of dehydro compound (8) : The dehydro compound (8 ; 700 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst (125 mg) at atmospheric pressure and room temperature for 18 h. The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was poured on to crushed ice. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water, and dried. It was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel. The benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) eluate gave a crystalline compound which was recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform-methanol, (ketal of methyl lantanolate), m.p. 226-229° (Found : M^+ , 498. Calcd. $C_{22}H_{50}O_4$: M, 498).

Acetylation of methyl lantanilate : Methyl lantanilate (1 g) dissolved in pyridine (10 ml) and acetic anhydride (12 ml) was heated on steam-bath for 1 h and worked up in the usual way. Tlc showed it to be a mixture of two products which were resolved by column chromatography over silica gel. One product which was crystallised from chloroform-ethanol mixture, (diacetate, 3), m.p. 156-158° (Found : C, 71.45 ; H, 8.72. $C_{28}H_{52}O_7$ calcd. C, 71.89 ; H, 8.96%).

The second compound was also crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, (mono-acetate, 1f) m.p. 233-235° (Found : C, 73.41 ; H, 9.42 ; M^+ , 542. $C_{28}H_{50}O_6$ calcd. C, 73.03 ; H, 9.29% ; M, 542). Acetylation of methyl lantanilate with Ac_2O/Py was carried out at 0°. On working up and resolution by chromatography over silica gel gave two products, one had m.p. 233-235° and found identical in every respect with monoacetate (1f). The other product, m.p. 227-229° was identified as methyl lantanilate.

Preparation of methyl 3-acetyl echinocystate : Methyl echinocystate (350 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) to which was added conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml) followed by water (1 ml) with shaking. The solution was kept at room temperature for 5 h after which it was poured on to ice. The precipitate was filtered, dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over Brockmann's alumina. Petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) eluate gave a fraction, m.p. 190-198°. It was crystallised from aqueous methanol and was identified as diacetyl methyl echinocystate by direct comparison of tlc, m.m.p. with authentic sample available in the laboratory. Petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) eluate gave a fraction crystallised from rectified spirit, 3-acetyl methyl echinocystate, m.p. 169-170° ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 28^\circ$ (dioxan). A dimorphic form of it after several crystallisation from methanol melted at 199-201° (Found :

C, 74.78; H, 9.82. $C_{33}H_{52}O_8$ calcd. C, 74.96; H, 9.91%.

Preparation of methyl 3-acetyl 15:16-dehydro-echinocystate (11): To a solution of methyl 3-acetyl echinocystate (500 mg) in dry pyridine (15 ml) cooled below 0° was added dropwise $POCl_3$ (7 ml) with stirring. The solution was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and then heated on steam bath for 1 h and poured on to crushed ice. The precipitate was filtered, dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The main fraction eluting out with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) mixture on crystallisation from MeOH had m.p. 193-194° (Found: C, 77.34; H, 9.89. $C_{33}H_{50}O_4$ calcd. C, 77.59; H, 9.86%) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 20^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). This compound consumed 1 mole of perbenzoic acid (1.32 N) in $CHCl_3$ solution in 24 h at 0° and after 7 days it consumed two moles of perbenzoic acid.

Hydrogenation of compound 11: Compound 11 (50 mg) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml) and hydrogenated at atmospheric pressure over PtO_2 catalyst. It was worked up in usual way, crystallised from rectified spirit and identified as acetyl methyl oleanolate, m.p. 218-220°. $[\alpha]_D + 70^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$).

Treatment of the anhydro compound (11) with OsO_4 : Compound 11 (50 mg) was dissolved in dry benzene (5 ml) and to it 5 drops of pyridine was added. To this was added with stirring a solution of OsO_4 (50 mg) in dry benzene (5 ml). The reaction mixture was kept in dark for 5 days. H_2S was passed through the solution and the black precipitate was filtered and the solvent was removed. The residue was identified as unreacted starting material (11).

Treatment of compound (8) with OsO_4 : Compound 8 (200 mg) was dissolved in dry benzene (20 ml) and to it 20 drops of pyridine was added and was stirred with a solution of OsO_4 (200 mg) in benzene (20 ml). The reaction mixture was kept in dark for 5 days. H_2S was passed and the product was worked up as described above. The product was found to contain mainly one compound and trace of another. The major compound was isolated by column chromatography, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (12a), m.p. 242° (Found: M^+ , 530. $C_{32}H_{50}O_8$ calcd.: M 530).

Acetylation of compound 12a: Compound 12a (100 mg) was acetylated by heating with Ac_2O (1 ml), pyridine (0.5 ml) on steam bath. The product was worked up in the usual way, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (12c), m.p. 239° (Found: C, 70.12; H, 8.98. $C_{36}H_{54}O_8$ calcd. C, 70.35; H, 8.79%).

Acetylation with Ac_2O and pyridine at 0° yielded a compound which was crystallised from aqueous methanol, (12d), m.p. 240° (Found: C, 71.14; H, 9.34. $C_{34}H_{52}O_7$ calcd. C, 71.32; H, 9.09%).

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